

FORMATION STAGES OF ANCIENT PERIOD DRESSES

Gulruh Sokhibbek qizi Tillaboyeva

Fergana state university , social and humanitarian sciences department teacher

ANNOTATION

This in the article ancient period of clothes formation stages scientific in terms of research matured _

Key nouns : clothes , head _ _ clothes _ _ clothes , fabric , linen fabric , cloth types , decoration elements , xenti , calaziris .

INTRODUCTION

Clothes society material and spiritual of culture structural is part of On the one hand , he is human work product as known one material to value have It is known that he died one Is it necessary? if satisfied , second on the other hand, it is practical and decorative art example is also Architectural constructions , work and marriage weapons like clothes too known one historical era , of the country natural climate the conditions of the people national to himself characteristics and his beauty about imagination about information gives _ Clothes and dress concepts content in terms of each other with common Although this is the case concepts between somewhat differences too there is

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Man of the body shape and to live style initial put on appearance set by Initial periods , that is primitive in the system an animal skin or plant varieties knitting based on certain one to form to be brought due to prepared cloth a person of the body known one parts to cover service did _ In this right rectangle cloth to the shoulder or to the groin thrown away , body around diagonal or circle according to horizontal in case connected . Connection to the place according to

they are from each other differentiated . In this way two type : shoulder and to the waist connectable clothes types appear was _ Theirs the most ancient shape foldable is clothes . It is the body wrap , to him different laces , belt and belts using fixed . Time go and get dressed new - on the shoulder throw away shape appear was _ To its structure according to one how many in the round was _ In particular , took open in type shoulder and two next to stitched if , the second type took closed is only _ shoulder and next to stare and head part and hand entrance for big there is

Egypt the world in history the most ancient state is counted . This country of humanity the most ancient culture from the hearths one being his _ history the following to periods being will be studied :

- a) ancient kingdom (3000-2400 BC) ;
- b) medium kingdom (2400-1710 BC) ;
- c) new kingdom (1580-1090 BC) .

Ancient Egyptians basically farming , farming and crafts (pottery , jewelry , weaving , glass work release) with were engaged in . My name is Q Egypt different castes , that is slaves , townspeople (artisans and mirzalar), freed slaves and from slaves consists of was _¹

From AD previous three a thousand of the year at the beginning Ancient Egypt big slavery state b died , him _ infinite to rule have has been pharaoh led by Egyptians Pharaoh of god on the ground shadow _ _ worshiped _ Especially religious priests to be of the priests of the pharaoh infinite rights protection by doing standing social we are unmatched and to oppression possibility created _

In ancient times Egyptians how much _ rich natural and cultural to riches have being them _ mastered don't be , they are nature events in front of powerless

¹ A bdull a house F. Uzbek _ language lexical a sinin b a' zi one m a' s a l a rig a d o ir . In the name of Pushkin Language and literature institute works t ' plant . Book 1. -T.: 1949, -29 pages . (Abdullaev F. On some issues of the lexicon of the Uzbek language . Collection of works of the Pushkin Institute Language oath Literature . Book 1. -T.: 1949, -29 pages .)

were _ This is the case their nature to the forces to their worship take came _ People to the sun , to the earth , to the moon , to the water , even animals (crocodile , wild boar , cow , hawk , snake and b. to), to plants worshiped _ Bin country of life different to the sides own effect passing came _ In particular , it is special in art place held _ Deified in things known one symbolic , conditional meaning leadership did _ In particular , a snake kingdom symbol if so , blue lily eternity and fertility symbol calculated .

Ancient Egypt in art a person image too _ conditional in character expressed . Mural images , statues their figure and actions known one criteria based on described _ Theirs cases and actions conditional to the character have _ Fig and in volume social come to exit big attention given _

Ancient Egypt statues , murals pictures this state culture , in particular , its sophistication and It 's a beauty about views about big information gives _ Persistence and conditionality behind ancient of the Egyptians aesthetic ideal signs k ' z thrown away These are tall b o' y , wide shoulders , narrow waist and bosom , big-big face signs . Especially Ancient _ in Egypt women g 's beauty about of views modern views with harmony attention pulls _ That's it period too tikkomat , on the face of characters accuracy and tenderness , tonsils appreciated .

Fabrics , color and ornaments . It is known from long ago Egypt linen homeland is considered To this the cause is the Nile River b ' thoughts linen cultivation for natural comfortable is the condition . Zig' ir from the fibers cloth in knitting Egyptians big to skill have those who are Saved cloth samples Egypt weavers skill proof gives _ The following evidence they are achieved results about sure imagination gives _ This period prepared 1 cm of fabric square 84 tan and 60 vodka threads conducted . 240 meters in length the eye almost unprogressive yarn there is only 1 gram organize did _ Weaver such thread only fingers through felt _ of Egypt linen from the fibers prepared cloth his own elegance with natural silk from fabrics did not stay . This of cloth five floor by doing clothes when sewing too from him a person body sure apparently standing _

Fabric invoice too each different was _ Especially new _ kingdom period gazmols invoice considerate _ Brush-like by doing woven gazmols gold threads and from him prepared different in forms decorations , glitter beads , various embroideries with decorated _ In this period also reticulated _ fabrics in consideration was _ White and white of fabric different appearances , especially , customs was _ Also floral _ fabrics too work issued _ In this white or full colorful to the base blue , orange , brown , yellow , green colorful images take down tradition was _ Black color mourning symbol was not

Fabrics whole to the surface geometric shapes (pathway1, wavy lines) image dropped . They are surroundings flowers , especially lilies _ flower leaf and common appearance , palm , reed , various plants leaves with decorated _ Noblemen clothes animals the image , in particular , with glasses snake - ureus , dung beetle , wings writing standing the falcon etc with decorated _

Ceremony dresses for linen _ of fabrics except skin and from fur too used .

RESULTS. Ancient Egypt of clothes in the form of draping is the main thing place _ holds _ Folds of clothing basically front on the side b die , get dressed back part light folded to the body stuck standing _ Your clothes back part not extended .

Ancient empire during men mainly « skhenti », i.e front band those who wore Scents form rectangle , or trapezoidal b died , various _ different in dimensions was _ Xhenti to the waist thin leather belt with tie , fasten placed _ Xentining over or of the body over rectangle shaped front band worn _²

Women dress of the body breast from the part until up to the calf part fixed standing tentacled of cloth consists of being , it is one or two tape with from the shoulder held worn _ Called Kalaziris _ this a sundress reminder clothes social come from the output strict look , he wants princess let it be concubine , all women for one different in the form was _ Women clothes only of fabric quality

² Tillaboyeva , GSQ (2022). In linguistics dress names _ *Scientific progress* , 3 (4), 506-514.

and expensive with differentiated . Medium kingdom to the period come Egypt of his wife in his dress change happened be started _ He is a little complexity and size one how many floor worn clothes at the expense of got bigger . Your clothes silhouette down towards expanded , pyramids shape take started _ Pleats , that is small nicknames wide apply started _

Men dress one how many floor by doing wearable from schenty consists of They died _ _ _ on top of each other worn _

Women dress big to changes did not meet Only noble women in their clothes ornaments type increased . Clothes of people social come exit said standing , that is to classes according to difference did _ If the rich linen fibrous of fabrics stitched clothes wore if so , of slaves clothes rough from the skin done _ Most high class people , in particular , pharaoh , ministers , priests , elders ground water of the owners clothes Angina decorated _ Medium kingdom to the period just come Egyptians of clothes shape somewhat has changed . As a result, he is one of the moment in itself on top of each other wearable one how many clothes apparently came _³ Clothes silhouette hem towards expanded , pyramidal to look came _ Pleasings wide q is used it happened Men clothes one how many thin from schenty consists of b o' lib , ustm a-ust worn _ Women clothes appearance it didn't change much . Only nobleman women their clothes decorate more k o' appeared . Clothes in the composition black colorful of the skin cloth from underneath sure as seen _ to stand importance given _ Collar instead of sail closed standing type bottle bead and precious stones with decorated decoration to tradition became _

New kingdom in the period (1580-1090 BC) in clothes classy difference more more felt started _ I am noble to their clothes used fabrics his own beauty , beauty , decoration of gold use with differs . This fabrics basically yarn and from

³ Um a r o v a . N . _ A lisher of n a v o i y a s a r l a l i s o n i y - concept _ _ _ _ t a research a v t o refer a t i F a r g ' o n a - 2021 - p.17 . Um a r o v a . N . _ A bstr a ct o f linguistic - conceptual _ _ _ _ rese a rch o f A lisher N a v o i ' s works _ _ Ferg a n a - 2021 - p.17 .

flax prepared _ from Sidon a slave women painted fabrics embroideries with decorated _ This of fabrics sewing don't dress to stare dullness special being , in them from pleats a lot used . Pleats of clothing whole tall equal to apply started _ However Egyptians pleated one how many from the place firmly that they put because of to action money did _

Clothes form big to change did not meet Even very twisted in clothes too to the body suitable dress to give aspiration it is felt . Such in me clothes free to action somewhat interrupt that he gave reason people while walking actions as learned _ impression wakes up .⁴

In this period male and women clothes to each other somewhat similar _ Men clothes pleating done skirt and from the cover consists of Various decoration and precious stones and guests with decorated big circle in the form of collars not only pharaoh and his family members as well nobleman apartments representatives too wear those who started Ceremony in their clothes skhenti , three angular front band saved . Lower layer clothes simply the rest Women jacket calaziris preserved the rest

Egyptians Syria pressing get dressed _ in culture somewhat change k ' z thrown away In particular , from Syria blanket , cloak-naramnik come in came _ Not only him men as well women too wear those who started It is a rectangle in the form of fabric for two folded , two next to stitched , of the head come in output for neck cut off long clothes was _ Women leathery front band and chest of drawers wore _⁵

Streams traditional clothes , in particular xentini save left _ Triangle front front band over one to the shoulder lion skin leave received _ The military front

⁴ Rustamovna , UN (2022). IN THE CATEGORY "CLOTHES". *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities* , 4 , 62-65.

⁵ Tillaboyeva , GSQ (2022). Alisher Navoi the concept of " personality " in his poetry . *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* , 2 (2), 182-196.

band and from the skin chest strap wore _ Village and city of kamba g' alari in his clothes change not observed .

Ancient mural pictures - in frescoes Egyptians basically walk described _ Palma leaves , papyrus , galda from the skin done sandals pharaoh as well his only those around wore _ Sandals simple in appearance they are _ you are welcome and without heels , bottom up fold raised , one how many narrow from the tapes consists of was _ To tags different different household and military appearances tims oli drawn _ Egyptians shoes simple in the form it is leather or from reeds processed slippers in the form of was _

CONCLUSION

Egyptians in his dress jewelry , in particular , hand and leg bracelets , rings , necklaces , earrings , bracelets and others separately place _ holds _ High to class belongs to people precious of metal made of stones with decorated jewelry items wearing if , lower class representatives paste and glazed from clay made decorations wearing walked _

Chief clothes shape differently they are _ of the owner social come exit said standing _ Ancient in David don't pharaoh head clothes front on the side rulership symbol – glasses snake with decorated crown and two layered striped (blue and yellow , gold color) , three corner in the style of folded big scarf in the form of was _

Pharaoh's woman the house or lily flower symbol dropped cap wore _ Priests ceremony during crocodile , falcon , h o' girl image dropped masks wore _

Women and men _ too plant fiber or a goat from wool done wigs wore _ Nobles . wigs small hair harvests or heard rope shaped hair from the harvest consists of was _ Slaves and farmers small wigs or linen from fabric caps wore _ Men their beards scratch walked _ Usually they are a goat from wool prepared artificial the beard lacquer with hardened metal _ threads with wrapping wearing walked _ Pharaoh's power cube or triangle shaped gold beard was _ Beard ties using modern in glasses like dujka using to the ear fixed .

Women to the face pink-red fat _ _ rub , eyelash and eyebrows to the black painted If so , men eyelashes green to color those who painted . Hand and leg his ears special plant - henna with reddish yellow to color painted _ Egypt dresses in the another nations to culture too own effect showing his _ elements row nations in their clothes tall showed .

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